

Abstract

Innovation in Emotionality: The Heidelberg Model of Chinese Medicine – An Integrative View Bridging Allopathic and Chinese Medicine in Psychosomatic Disease.

Maria João Santos^{1,2*}, Nuno Correia³, Maria Begoña Criado⁴, Catarina Pereira^{2,5}, Sónia Silva², Jorge Machado⁵, and Henry Johannes Greten⁶.

¹ Neurosciences Institute Prof. Dr. Manuel Laranjeira, Porto, Portugal;

² C+ Health Academy, Matosinhos, Porto, Portugal;

³ Department of Internal Medicine, Trofa Saúde Private Hospital, Gaia, Portugal;

⁴ 1H-TOXRUN - One Health Toxicology Research Unit, University Institute of Health Sciences (IUCS), CESPU, Gandra, Portugal;

⁵ ICBAS – School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal;

⁶ Heidelberg School of Chinese Medicine, Heidelberg, Germany.

* Correspondence: mjr.mtc@gmail.com

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Background: Since antiquity, emotions and feelings have been recognised as fundamental drivers of disease. The increasing clinical emphasis on the body-mind connection in both somatic and mental disorders challenges traditional Western medical paradigms regarding pathogenesis. Conversely, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) has historically observed all expressions of life, categorising emotions as diagnostically relevant components of broader clinical patterns. This has led to a systematic arrangement of signs and symptoms, resulting in unique diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

Methodology: This work presents an integrated review of Eastern and Western emotional theories to facilitate a semantic-conceptual comparison between TCM and Western medicine. Specifically,

"modern cortical readout theories" were compared with the Heidelberg Model (HM) of TCM. The review highlights the differences and convergences between these two medical perspectives regarding the nature and impact of emotions.

Conclusion: The findings of this review indicate that Western neuroscientific models of emotion and the Heidelberg Model of TCM converge significantly. This trans-cultural and conceptual comparison of medical paradigms allows for the seamless integration of both perspectives in clinical intervention and research. Such a bridge enables a more sophisticated and effective conceptualisation of psychosomatic diseases in modern practice.

Keywords: Emotionality; Emotions; Heidelberg Model of TCM; Chinese Medicine; Psychosomatic Diseases.

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